

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component *m*-3M3FBS Analogs Evaluated as PLC γ 2 Chemical Probes

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Introduction:

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS), whole-genome sequencing, and gene-expression network analyses comparing normal aged brain tissues to brain tissues from patients diagnosed with late-onset Alzheimer's disease (LOAD) have identified protective and risk genes involved in microglial function and neuroinflammation. PLC γ 2 encodes the 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2) enzyme, which converts phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate [PI(4,5)P $_2$] into 1D-myoinositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP $_3$) and diacylglycerol (DAG) (**Figure 1A**). PLC γ 2 is mainly expressed in immune cells and microglia and sparsely expressed in other brain cells, such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.¹ A rare coding variant of PLC γ 2, *PLCG2*^{P522R}, has been identified using whole exome microarray analysis² and observed in various populations.^{3,4,5} This variant confers a protective effect. Alzheimer's disease patients expressing this variant exhibit a slower rate of cognitive decline than those who do not.² While the exact mechanism(s) of this protective effect is not fully understood, this variant has

Figure 1. PLC γ 2 domains. Structural depiction based on PDB 6PBC of PLC γ 1.

been characterized as a functional hypermorph.¹ Therefore, pharmacological intervention that increases the activity of wild-type PLC γ 2 is a potential therapeutic strategy to reduce the rate of cognitive decline in Alzheimer's patients.

PLC γ 2 is a complex multidomain protein that exists in an autoinhibited state with a regulatory domain blocking the enzyme's ability to bind to its substrate, phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂), at the cell membrane surface (**Figure 1**). Although the process of PLC γ 2 regulation is not fully understood, much can be inferred from the known roles of spleen tyrosine kinase (SYK), B cell linker (BLNK), and Bruton's agammaglobulinemia tyrosine kinase (BTK) in B cells^{6,7,8,9} and studies of 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-1 (PLC γ 1) using hydrogen–deuterium exchange (HDX).¹⁰ SYK is activated in the triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) pathway and phosphorylates BLNK, enabling the formation of the SYK– PLC γ 2–BTK activation complex (**Figure 2**). This complex potentially initiates the separation of PLC γ 2's regulatory domain from its catalytic site, priming the enzyme for full activation. PLC γ 2 is then phosphorylated by SYK and BTK at multiple sites, with Tyr759 being the most crucial. Phosphorylated Tyr759 binds an arginine-rich pocket within the cSH2 domain of PLC γ 2, disrupting key interactions with the catalytic core and exposing membrane-binding surfaces and the active site. Molecular dynamics simulations have shown that the P522R protective variant causes a significant change in the position, structure, and flexibility of the nSH2 domain.¹¹ Thus, one possible strategy to activate PLC γ 2 would be identifying molecules that bind at the SH2 domain interface and breaking interactions with the catalytic core domains.

Figure 2. Proposed mechanism of PLC γ enzymes transitioning from the autoinhibited to the active state. (Created in BioRender).

Two molecules have been reported to activate phospholipase C (PLC) enzymes, U73122 (1-(6-((17 β -3-methoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-yl)amino)hexyl)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione)¹² and *m*-3M3FBS (**1**) (2,4,6-trimethyl-N-(meta-3-trifluoromethyl-phenyl)-benzenesulfonamide).¹³ U73122 was originally identified as a PLC inhibitor¹⁴ and has been used extensively as the prototypical PLC enzyme inhibitor in cell culture^{15,16,17,18,19}; however, U73122 has been shown to activate PLC β and PLC γ family members *in vitro*.¹² U73122 has also recently been shown to affect numerous other cellular proteins, including phospholipase D,²⁰ 5-lipoxygenase,²¹ calcium channels,²² potassium channels,²³ telomerase,²⁴ histamine H1 receptor,²⁵ and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase.²⁶ This complete lack of specificity is unsurprising since the maleimide of U73122 can react with thiol in cysteine residues. Therefore, U73122 likely reacts nonspecifically with exposed cysteines on numerous cellular proteins. This lack of specificity

and high reactivity make U73122 a poor choice as a chemical probe for studying the pharmacology of PLC activation and an unsuitable starting point for developing selective PLC γ 2 activators.

m-3M3FBS was originally identified from a screen of compounds that enhanced superoxide-generating activity in human neutrophils.¹³ Its activity was proposed to be caused by the direct activation of PLCs. Supporting this proposition, several laboratories have demonstrated intracellular calcium release, a downstream signaling effect of PLC activation, in various cell types treated with *m*-3M3FBS.^{27,28,29,30,31} However, the potency and specificity of *m*-3M3FBS-mediated PLC activation are debated due to reports that intracellular calcium release occurs before PLC activity is detected³² and that *m*-3M3FBS affects the inward and outward flow of ions in a PLC-independent manner, possibly through the direct inhibition of delayed rectifier potassium channels.³³ Additionally, *m*-3M3FBS is cytotoxic in some cell lines.^{28,29,30} Thus, it is unclear whether *m*-3M3FBS exerts its activity primarily through PLC activation and, if it does, whether analogs selective for PLC γ 2 can be identified. No selective small molecule activators of PLC γ 2 are currently known; thus, there is a clear need to identify such an activator to determine whether the pharmacological activation of PLC γ 2 is a viable therapeutic strategy to treat Alzheimer's disease.

Figure 3. Structures of *m*-3M3FBS, *o*-3M3FBS, and structural analogs.

1 (*m*-3M3FBS), the reported inactive analog **2** (*o*-3M3FBS), and a set of analogs (**Figure 3** and **Table 1**) were acquired via either synthesis or purchase to assess the effectiveness and feasibility of *m*-3M3FBS analogs as PLC γ 2 activators. These compounds have been evaluated using numerous assay classes, namely, target engagement utilizing cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA),³⁴ affinity selection mass spectrometry (ASMS),³⁵ biochemical activity employing the fluorogenic probe XY-69,³⁶ and cellular activity testing for phagocytosis. CETSA assesses cellular target engagement by quantifying changes in protein thermal stability upon ligand binding to endogenous proteins in intact cells.³⁴ A split Nano Luciferase (SplitLuc CETSA) version of the assay was utilized to provide sufficient throughput^{37,38} for structure–activity relationship (SAR) studies.^{37,38} HMC3 cells were stably transfected with HiBit-PLC γ 2 to enable protein expression in a physiologically relevant cellular context. The thermal stability of this HiBit-labeled

protein in intact cells was measured in the following two formats. In the initial screen, cells were treated in 96-well plates with FBS analogs at a single concentration (100 μ M) at 37°C for 60 min and then exposed to a 3-min isothermal heating step at 45.9°C (experimentally determined T_m of HiBit-PLC γ 2). Luminescence detection was then conducted with the Nano-Glo HiBit Lytic detection kit (Promega, Cat. N3040).³⁸ Compound treatment was performed in triplicate, and raw signals were normalized to the mean of the controls (in the same plate) as percentage of control. When the difference in compound-treated cells > control mean + 3SD, the compound was considered positive and selected for further testing with a dose–response CETSA. In the dose–response CETSA, cells were treated with decreasing concentrations from 100 μ M with 1:3 serial dilutions to generate an 8-point curve. An AC_{50} was calculated with the percentage of control data using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model, and the percent luminescence remaining at the highest concentration was reported for the compounds when the difference from the DMSO control exceeded 3x the standard deviation (SD). Otherwise, an AC_{50} was not calculated. These dose–response CETSA data (**Figure 4** and **Table 2**) indicate that several analogs demonstrated superior target engagement compared to **1**. However, numerous analogs exhibited a similar response in the absence of the PLC γ 2 enzyme, indicating the potential promiscuity of these compounds or the possibility of a false positive result. Only **5** and **11** showed evidence of target engagement without a significant signal loss in the HiBit-only control.

Compound	Name	MW (g/mol)	cLogP ⁱ	cLogD ⁱⁱ	tPSA ⁱⁱⁱ	H-bond donors	H-bond acceptors	Lipinski violations ^{iv}	CNS MPO score ^v
1	<i>m</i> -3M3FBS	343.4	5.2	3.7	46.2	1	3	1	4.00
2	<i>o</i> -3M3FBS	343.4	4.7	3.0	46.2	1	3	0	4.50
3		300.4	3.9	2.7	70.0	1	4	0	5.10
4		301.3	3.7	2.6	46.2	1	3	0	5.20
5		289.4	4.5	3.4	46.2	1	3	0	4.40
6		329.3	4.5	3.3	46.2	1	3	0	4.50
7		325.4	5.9	4.4	46.2	1	3	1	3.80
8		336.2	2.9	2.0	46.2	1	3	0	5.80
9		370.2	4.9	3.7	46.2	1	3	0	3.90
10		394.2	4.9	3.6	46.2	1	3	0	3.80
11		282.4	3.0	0.8	58.2	2	4	0	4.50

Table 1. Arylsulfonamide compounds reported in the literature and selected analogs ⁱChemAxon calculated the partition coefficient of the ratio of the concentration of the compound in octanol to its concentration in water. ⁱⁱChemAxon calculated octanol-water distribution coefficient (from pKa and cLogP); ⁱⁱⁱTopological polar surface area (\AA^2) based on the method of Ertl *et al.*;³⁹ ^{iv}See Lipinski *et al.*;⁴⁰ ^vCentral Nervous System Multiparameter Optimization score based on the method of Wager *et al.*⁴¹

Compound	AC_{50} (μ M) ⁱ	HiBit-PLC γ 2 % ⁱⁱ	HiBit only % ⁱⁱⁱ
1	NC	105	N.T.
2	NC	102	N.T.
3	NC	90	N.T.
4	NC	65	82
5	>100	54	96
6	99	51	74
7	NC	78	104
8	>100	66	44
9	71	32	38
10	57	18	40
11	NC	64	99

Table 2. Cellular thermal shift assay results. ⁱConcentration (μM) that induced a half-maximum loss of luminescence (AC_{50}) compared to the control. ⁱⁱPercent luminescence at the highest dose (100 μM) compared to the control (DMSO). ⁱⁱⁱPercent luminescence at the highest dose (100 μM) with HiBit only compared to the control (DMSO).

Figure 4. Representative CETSA dose-response curves. ● HiBit-PLCy2, ▲ HiBit only.

Affinity selection mass spectrometry (ASMS) was employed to test a subset of compounds as an orthogonal approach to investigating the target engagement of this series. A dose range of 100–0.05 μM was applied in 384-well low-volume polypropylene microtiter plates; a solution of PLCy2 (final concentration 400 nM) was transferred to biochip arrays functionalized with a Tris-Ni-NTA-presenting self-assembled monolayer to immobilize the His-tagged protein. The arrays were incubated for 90 min in a humidified chamber to prevent evaporation and allow for specific immobilization of the His-PLCy2 protein and any bound small molecules. The arrays were purified by a rapid <3-second gentle wash step with deionized ultrafiltered water and dried with compressed air. ASMS was performed using the reflector positive mode on an AB Sciex TOF-TOF 5800 System (AB Sciex, Framingham, MA). While ATP showed clear separation from the background signal, neither **1** nor **2** indicated substantial evidence of target engagement (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Affinity selection mass spectrometry (ASMS) ● PLC γ 1, ■ PLC γ 2, ▲ Background.

Sondek and coworkers described an assay for PLC γ 1 activity in the presence of liposomes as a model for activity at the cell membrane where the natural ligand is located.³⁶ The assay was developed for PLC γ 2 at the Purdue Institute for Drug Discovery. Liposomes containing XY-69 (purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids, cat. # 850168) were generated using phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) and 1-stearoyl-2-arachidonoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylethanolamine (lipidPE). The PLC γ 2 enzyme was exposed to this solution, and after treatment with the compounds of interest, the fluorescence intensity (ex: 485 nm; em: 520 nm) was recorded every 2 min for 120 min (**Figure 6**). The slope of the linear portion of the curves (up to 50 min) was compared to the control to obtain the relative reaction rate. Dose-dependency curves of a representative sample of the compounds tested are shown (**Figure 7**).

Both aromatic rings tolerate a wide range of substitutions; however, in nearly all instances, this activity is lost when the rings are replaced with aliphatic functionality. For example, **11** showed no enzymatic activation at a single dose of 100 μ M; thus, it was not submitted for dose-response testing. Several compounds containing sulfonamide linker alterations (reverse sulfonamide, sulfonate, sulfide, and amine) retained activity, while others (amide, sulfone, and sulfoxide) did not.

The reported PLC activator **1** (*m*-3M3FBS) produced one of the highest increases among all analogs tested. As expected, the change in slope of the reported inactive analog **2** (*o*-3M3FBS) was much lower, although it still showed a significant increase in activation.

Figure 6. Progress curves for the hydrolysis of XY-69 by PLC γ 2 in the presence and absence of compound **6** in the liposomal biochemical assay. The fluorescence intensity of the generated product was measured as a function of time and the following concentrations of compound **6**: \blacktriangle 122.5 μ M, \blacktriangleleft 40.0 μ M, \blacktriangleright 12.5 μ M, \bullet 5.00 μ M, \blacklozenge 1.00 μ M, \blacktriangledown 0.325 μ M, \blacktriangledup 0.100 μ M, \blacktriangleleft 0.025 μ M, \bullet 0 control.

Figure 7. Kinetic response of PLC γ 2 to increasing concentrations of compounds in the presence of XY-69 using the liposomal biochemical assay. The rates of the reaction as RFI/min are plotted as a function of compound concentration for each compound shown: A) ● 1, ▲ 10, ■ 6, ● 3, ◆ 9 B) ★ 7, ▲ 5, ● 2, ■ 4, ▼ 8. The rates of the reaction were normalized to the values at zero activator concentration.

A phenotypic high-content imaging assay with simultaneous measures of phagocytosis, cell number, and nuclear intensity was used to assess cellular pharmacology and health. The model cell lines BV2 (immortalized mouse microglia, a gift from Dr. Michelle Block's laboratory at IUSM) and HMC3 (immortalized human microglia, obtained from ATCC, CRL-3304) were used to provide adequate throughput. Cells were cultured in DMEM GlutaMax media (ThermoFisher) containing 10% FBS and Pen-Strep in a 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator, plated in Corning Falcon 384 well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates; 400 cells/45 µl/well (BV2 cells), 600 cells/45 µl/well (HMC3 cells) and 2000 cell/45 µl/well (primary cells), and treated with 10x serially diluted compounds (60 µM–3 nM) for 48 hrs at 37°C. The cells were then seeded with pHrodo-myelin (20 hrs total) 24 hrs after compound treatment initiation; 1 mg/ml (protein equivalent) pHrodo-myelin stocks were stored at -20°C or -80°C, thawed, diluted with culture media to produce a 10x seeding solution (50 µg/ml) and added to the 384-well plate (5 µl/well). Nuclear staining solution (1 µl of 10 mg/ml Hoechst-33342 per 1 ml culture media; 20 µl/well) was added to a final concentration of 2.5 µg/ml, and the plates were incubated for 30 min at 37°C and then scanned with an ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system (10x objective lens, 4 fields/well collected). The mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, total cell counts per well, and mean average nuclear intensity per cell for cell health were measured. Cellular potencies for each endpoint (EC₅₀ for phagocytosis, IC₅₀ for cell count) were calculated using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model.

Compound	Name	Ave. % Phagocytosis @ 60 µM ⁱ		Ave. % Cell Count @ 60 µM ⁱ		N
		HMC3 cells	BV2 cells	HMC3 cells	BV2 cells	
1	<i>m</i> -3M3FBS	1 (2)	0 (0)	6 (5)	8 (10)	3
2	<i>o</i> -3M3FBS	117 (32)	107 (7)	89 (24)	92 (23)	3
3		111 (8)	113 (44)	79 (17)	85 (20)	2
4		89 (20)	106 (6)	84 (16)	95 (22)	2
5		111	165	78	45	1
6		47 (41)	118 (27)	62 (76)	42(55)	2
7 ⁱⁱ		110 (16)	119 (25)	94 (12)	89 (8)	2
8		104 (6)	114 (6)	88 (19)	86 (14)	2
9		281	581	16	9	1
10		93	434	11	1	1
11		146	225	65	63	1

Table 3. Phagocytosis results ⁱPercent luminescence at the highest dose (60 µM) compared to the control. Standard deviations are given in paratheses where applicable. ⁱⁱData reported for 20 µM.

Ideally, a PLCy2 activator would induce an increase in phagocytosis at a lower concentration than that resulting in the onset of a cell count decrease. Any apparent increase in cell activity accompanied by a sharp decline in cell count confounds interpretation. Many FBS analogs showed no significant increase in phagocytosis; in the case of **5**, **9**, and **10**, the increase was paired with a sharp cell count decline (**Table 3** and **Figures 8** and **9**). The exception was **11**, which still demonstrates a moderate degree of potential cytotoxicity.

Primary mouse microglia isolated from mouse brains were periodically tested in the phagocytosis assay to verify that readouts from the BV2 and HMC3 cells are mechanistically similar to those obtained with primary cells. Primary microglia were obtained from B6J neonatal mouse (P0–P3) cortical tissue, which was homogenized in DMEM, filtered through 250 and 100 µm mesh, and cultured in Advanced DMEM/F12+10% FBS, 1x GlutaMAX and 1x Pen/Strep. At 21 days *in vitro* (DIV), the cultures were subjected to mild trypsinization using 0.083% Trypsin-EDTA in DMEM for 30 min to detach an intact layer

of astrocytes. A select number of cell active FBS analogs were tested in these cells. Unfortunately, there was little to no increase in phagocytosis (**Figure 10**).

Physicochemical and ADME properties were determined using the following assays: microsomal stability intrinsic clearance (Cl_{int}) in mouse liver microsomal solution, MDCK permeability (P_{app}), protein binding (f_u) in mouse plasma, and kinetic solubility in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer (**Table 4**). Many of these analogs performed poorly in these assays, particularly in the microsomal stability intrinsic clearance assay, where many failed to produce any meaningful response.

Figure 8. Phagocytosis in HMC3 cells. ● Cell count, ■ Nuclear intensity, ▲ Phagocytosis.

Figure 9. Phagocytosis in BV2 cells. ● Cell count, ■ Nuclear intensity, ▲ Phagocytosis.

Rigorously validated molecular tools are essential for investigating the biological function of PLCy2 and studying the pharmacology of PLCy2 activation⁴². Thus, we have developed assays and characterized reported activators to further advance research in this area. Although many FBS analogs showed activation capabilities in the biochemical XY-69 assay, most failed to show significant levels of target engagement or increased phagocytosis in primary mouse microglia cells. These results and the poor performance in ADME assays indicate that **1** is a poor starting point for a PLCy2 drug discovery program.

We have screened for novel activators, characterized them in the assays described here, and evaluated the systemic and central exposure of these compounds in mice. The results of this work will be reported in due course.

Figure 10. Phagocytosis in primary mouse microglia cells. ● Cell count, ■ Nuclear intensity, ▲ Phagocytosis

Compound	Cl_{int} ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$) ⁱ	P_{app} ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}/\text{s}$) ⁱⁱ	f_u ⁱⁱⁱ	Kinetic solubility (μM) ^{iv}
1	*	*	NT	21-40
3	*	69.8	0.0003	81-100
4	607.7	79.7	NT	>100
6	*	17.1	0.003	61-80
7	*	37.4	NT	41-60
8	77.8	95.0	0.0193	>100

Table 4. Measured physicochemical and ADME properties. * = Assays failed when tested. NT = not tested. ⁱIntrinsic clearance in mouse liver microsomes. ⁱⁱMDCK permeability assay as an estimate of intestinal absorption. ⁱⁱⁱMouse plasma fraction unbound. ^{iv}Kinetic solubility in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer.

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